

Methodology of Improving the Effectiveness of Radical Transformation of Lesson Structure

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Abstract:

This article aims to dramatically change the classroom structure of the instructor, not only to ensure that qualitative and effective lessons are organized in small groups, but also in the use of collaborative learning, and that students are acquiring knowledge at the nearest intellectual development level. The methodology for improving the efficiency of achievement is described.

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Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 14, 2018 N PP-3907 "On measures to bring the youth upbringing, education and upbringing to a qualitatively new level" of September 5, 2018 Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to improve the system of management of public education" of September 5, 2018 № PP-3931 Statement by President Mirziyoyev Sh.Mirziyoyev on August 23, 2019 "On the issues of upbringing of young people in the spirit of patriotism and enhancing the role of teachers in the society" Secondary schools based on the ideas of President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyayev to improve the quality and effectiveness of the lessons and to enhance the prestige and social status of teachers. The results of our research have shown that the decisions and decisions of the heads of secondary schools, especially teachers, by the President and the Government, aimed at radically changing the system of public education, are not up to date. In order to eliminate this shortcoming, the President's decrees, resolutions, Appeals and resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan emphasize that widespread advocacy among educational institutions has become a vital necessity and urgently needs to start this work.

Today's teacher must be able to differentiate between traditional education, modern traditional education, and modern forms of education in order to meet the demands of the day. Most teachers understand modern traditional education, modern education.

Classical traditional education consists of teacher training, students being able to quietly master this knowledge, to apply them to practice in or outside the classroom, and to work independently with the book. This process, that is, classical traditional education, is called didactography in science.

Contemporary traditional education consists of a combination of religious studies, information and communication technologies and interactive teaching methods.

Modern education is a complex use of ICT tools and interactive methods in training, aimed at children acquiring knowledge based on their children's interactions based on their interactions, and using these knowledge in a changing environment. education is said to guarantee the formation of practical skills and qualifications.

We are committed to teaching each student two levels of intellectual development.

Level 1 The true level of intellectual development of the student. At the same time, the student performs the tasks independently without any external assistance.

Level 2 The nearest intellectual development level of the learner. At the same time, the student completed the learning tasks with little external assistance, such as using books, people around the Internet or the Internet.

Symbolically, the levels of intellectual development of the student can be explained as follows:

The first is that a car is drowning in mud and its wheels are spinning, but not moving.

The second level could be compared to the one with the slightest protection on the back of a light-watered car.

Of course, life is needed. Therefore, it is useful to teach in the classroom, taking into account the nearest intellectual development level of the learner. Because the student will not be able to do what he did yesterday, and the next day he will be able to do it independently. In each such lesson, the level of intellectual development of each student rarely exceeds. Such training is called developing education.

Achieving quality and effectiveness in education should begin with improving the quality and effectiveness of each lesson. For this purpose, it is necessary to achieve optimization in teacher work. Optimality means that the teacher achieves the highest educational goals, with less time, less effort and less resources in organizing and conducting lessons.

In order to improve the quality and effectiveness of teaching in schools, it is necessary to create a modern lesson plan (syllabus, syllabus), to include glossaries of important concepts within a specific topic, and to make the lesson more active for students. - we need to move to organized small groups.

Small groups have random, voluntary, and forced forms. The subgroup that we propose must consist of at least 1 Excellent, 1 Good Learner, 2 Medium Learning, and 1 Poor Learner. Volunteerism and the students' wishes are also taken into account when forming small groups.

Classes are 5x5x1 (meaning: I have five subgroups, each has five students, the same task for everyone), 5x5x2 (meaning: I have a small group of five, each has five students, and they have two different tasks, namely 1, 3, The same task for subgroups of 5,

and assignments to subgroups 2 and 4 are identical to the ones assigned to odd subgroups, but have different content), 5x5x5 (meaning: I have five subgroups in the class, each I have five students, each student individually).

Suppose there are 28 students in the classroom. Of these 25, 5 subgroups are formed. A small subgroup will be formed from the remaining 3 best students.

The text of the new theme is divided into 5 parts depending on the content. Five copies of each part are prepared and distributed to small groups. The first part is presented to the first subgroup, and the fifth part of the text is given to the fifth subgroup, that is, the subcategories of the text divided into five sections, corresponding to their numbers.

Each student in a small group consisting of the best students in the class will be given three copies of the entire text of the new lesson, one for each.

If any student of a subgroup, for any objective reason, fails to attend the class, his role will be replaced by one of these 3 excellent students.

In the next lesson, the topic of the study will be divided into 5 parts, each of which will be assigned as homework in the previous lesson so that it can be used in small groups accordingly.

Students complete these homework assignments.

Each piece of text that students read at home is prepared by the teacher in 5 copies and presented to the small group leaders corresponding to their numbers. The leader will distribute these copies to his teammates. Each subgroup learns and re-reads the text he / she has received (actually learning the text at home) for 3 minutes and the other 5 students discuss it together for 3 minutes.

The number one students of all subgroups are distributed to the first subgroup, and the other subgroups are subdivided into their own numbers and form new subgroups, symbolically traveling. The newly formed subgroups have the same number of pupils, that is, the first newly formed subgroup, all the first number students in the first subgroups, and the 5th newly formed subgroups all the fifth digit students in the first subgroups.

The newly formed subgroups will dissolve 3 excellent students who have learned the whole text. They carefully listen to the statements of their students in small groups and find out what they do not know, and fill in the ideas they have left behind.

For example, the first student of the first subgroup will be in his or her group and will be welcomed by the other subgroups "Welcome" to the number one, "Assalomu alaykum". It takes about 1 minute to spread.

For newly formed subgroups, for example, in the fifth subgroup, the fifth person from the first subgroup begins, the second one from the second subgroup, the fifth from the third subgroup, the fifth from the fourth subgroup The reader, and the last, the fifth student of the fifth subgroup, who is the host, tells the story and concludes with a coherent text of the new theme. Each student is given up to 5 minutes to tell his or her own mantle. After that, students will return to their destination. It will take another minute. Students returning home from the trip will share the information they have learned with their early teammates. It takes about 5 minutes. Students will be given homework for the remaining 2 minutes.

By analyzing the process outlined above, the new theme is part of a holistic text that is studied and put into practice by the reader 7 times: 1) a piece of text is given for home study; 2) this text will be repeated in the class for 3 minutes; 3) Subgroup members discuss this text for 3 minutes; 4) inform the newly formed subgroup of the group on the journey within 5 minutes, or write the formulas; 6) Discuss within 5 minutes after returning from the tour, in the first subgroup, on the whole text of the new lesson; 7) Each subgroup will be given homework for the remaining 2 minutes, with examples, questions, exercises, etc. that apply the learning material on the whole text of the new topic studied.

Not only does this work provide quality and effective lessons, students also acquire knowledge at the highest level of intellectual development, meet international academic research needs, but also a freelance thinker whose primary purpose is to educate, understand his / her responsibility before society, state and family. education of active citizens, and the surplus of the country's human resources.

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